

Sowing Synergy: Integrating Traditional and Modern Knowledge for Agricultural Sustainability

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The agricultural landscape of India is deeply intertwined with traditional knowledge that has been passed down through generations. These methods are shown to deeply understand local ecosystems, crop cycles, and environmental changes. Despite challenges, there has been a concerted effort to fuse indigenous practices with modern agricultural technologies. This amalgamation aims to preserve traditional knowledge while optimizing crop productivity, resource efficiency, and resilience to climate change. Integrating these two knowledge systems presents challenges, but through an interdisciplinary approach, we can identify synergies and trade-offs and achieve a balanced and sustainable agricultural paradigm. This presentation contributes to the global discourse on sustainable agriculture, offering lessons and recommendations applicable not only to India but also to regions facing similar challenges worldwide.